

AN APPROACH TO CREATE SPEAKING ACTIVITIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583844>

Abstract. The primary aim of early foreign language learning is on development of oral skills. During learning FL Speaking is reproductive and imitative and activities focus at the production of closely supported exact output. But, formation of fluency and basic speaking competencies consist more than just producing memorized chunks of language. In other word progress in their acquisition of the target language and to become truly communicatively competent, learners also need to be able to utilize language spontaneously and creatively. This article proposes an approach to improve discursive skills in the development of oral speech.

Key words: communicative tasks, language acquisition, formulaic expressions, experimental language use, model of creative speaking, useful approach and methods for young learners, improvisation activities

Finally, it develops a model of creative speaking that demonstrates how young learners can be supported in deliberately developing the skills for a more independent language use. The main purpose of foreign language learning early is the development of communicative competence, with the attention on the oral skills of listening and speaking. Especially at the beginning, speaking in this content is reproductive and simple, giving your young beginner learners the possibility to practice language patterns as well as to master basic communicative conditions, for instance, presenting themselves with the aid of simple rote-learned phrases. This aim is also reflected in plentiful textbooks for these young learners, in which the great deal of speaking activities goal at the production of guided clear output. It may take into account form of dialogue, for example, for which the learners are provided with questions and answers that they are able to change by inserting various lexical sources into open slots in the given sentence structure. Such kind of activities can be encouraging, because they allow young learners to active attempt in the lesson and to interact successfully in the target language at an early point in the learning process. Learner correlation in both contexts was restricted to the utilize of prefabricated expressions, and that

creativity "involved either selection of prefabricated exponents from materials already practiced, or oral 'gap-filling'(Mitchell and Lee 2003,55).

More and more scientists claim that the learners' target language production often limited to the utilize of formulaic sequences. Children could use prefabricated expressions in conversational interaction, but that they often had troubles in constructing their own sentences. As the development of fluency and basic speaking competencies demands more than just producing memorized chunks of language, learners need chances to use language spontaneously under what Thornbury(2005a,13) calls 'real operating condions', in order to progress in their acquisition of the target language and to become communicatively competent. Using the target language creatively perhaps a significant motivational factor for the children:

'In order to keep the joy, enthusiasm and ambition of young learners alive, it is absolutely vital to provide them with more chances to discover and experiment with the language and to give more attention the creative and productive learning process'. A key question is therefore how it is possible to integrate such opportunities into lessons for young learners. Here, the utilize of more open communicative activities seems to be an useful approach. Indispensable activities could contain communicative tasks and improvisation activities, as they have the potential to initiate language use that transcends formulae and reproduction.

In this article, we aim to contribute to the understanding of communicative competence in the young learners' classroom by introducing research based model of creative speaking. At first, result of research into task-based work with them as well as examples of their task-based language production, are considered as a more open and flexible alternative to communicative tasks, which also provides various possibilities for children to work independently with the language sources that is already available to them.

A task - based approach has great potential when the purpose is to engage learners in conversational interaction that allows them to creatively make their utterances. One meaning of a communicative task that sums the main characteristics commonly attributes to tasks is the one offered by Ellis (2009,223). He exactly describes a communicative task as a meaning-focused activity, which includes a need to convey information and enables learners to utilize the linguistic means available to them in order to work towards an accurately defined outcomes(Ellis 2003,2009,223). Thus, communicative tasks maintain negotiation of meaning communicative in situations in which the

attention is on task completion. Learners can benefit from the interaction that task-based work, because that are exposed to meaningful input and receive feedback on the language they produce as well as chances for producing shifted output(Long 1996;Swain 1993).By the way ,Pinter(2007)examined 10-year-old hungarian learners of English who again and worked with information –gap tasks .These tasks allowed the learners to' express their own meanings in a less restrained manner'(Pinter 2007,189).The aim of the study was to observe changes in the learners' performance and the gains task-based interaction with this age group can lead to the repeated use of tasks not only resulted in a more fluent language use, but also led learners to respond to and to assist each other in the interaction ,while initially they simply displayed their knowledge of English. These results provide evidence for the beneficial effects of utilizing tasks with young learners .However, when comparing the task-based interactions of them to those contrasts task more effectively .They focused on problem-solving and completing the task, while the 10-year-old children who were observed basically seemed to name things in their picture ,which did not prove equally effective . These differences may be identified to the young learners' cognitive development but Pinter also point outs the possibility that the children's approach is an impact of familiar classroom practices , namely 'the dominant classroom discourse of naming things that the children are so utilized to'(Pinter 2006,626)

Tasks as capacities for creative speaking. Two learners have to work together and use the target language to exchange information in order to be able to identify five diversities in the picture.This kind of date reflects 'learners' capacity to utilize their interlanguage (IL) grammar under the time constraints of spontaneous oral language production .Therefore , it naturally involves errors and thus provides insights into the learners' current stage of interlanguage development. Also ,the format of an information –gap task was maintained , as the learners were each given a picture of a monster and had to identify five differences between the picture through talking to each other . The task allowed the children to rely on their own linguistic repertoire .The following examples of learners interactions show how this may promote the creative and productive use of the language.

Improvisation activities. This kind of and drama activities have a number of advantages for foreign language learning .In order to become naturally communicatively competent , learners have to be provided with manifold capacities to become autonomous language users by activities that support their natural desire to interact with peers and allow them to make use of their ' rich

source of imagination, creativity, curiosity, and playfulness' On the basis of the finding discussed above, a creative speaking approach was enhanced with the aim to maintain productive language use in the young learners' classroom. It is demonstrated in the model in Fig.1 and is described in the following sections. Fig.1 An approach to creative speaking .

To my way of thinking , watching cartoons ,movies ,shows,interesting TV programs can help to enhance speaking ,not only speaking but also listening abilities in various age. By the way , only watching this kind of items is not very profitable that's to say person who are watching(for example, ted.talks) should notice some new phrases, sentences,main ideas of speech and so on during watching and listening.After finished watching , person who are watched have to speak to partner.

After some months, each group of students was interviewed and asked quiz questions to identify their result. Their speech and intonation were estimated separately. Finally asked for their views on the training system. The results illustrated that group 1 students were dissatisfied with the old methodology and encountered obstacles in speaking.Cases of discomfort and excitement were observed in public and when talking to a stranger. Apparently, there are no requisitions to enhance the ability to speak, only 30% of them, group 3 students were able to speak without difficulty, 40% were able to answer average questions, and the remaining 30% of students only the ability to answer general questions was achieved. Students in groups 2 and 3 illustrated almost the same result. It is clear that improving English speaking skills depends on practice. It was observed that via this experience not only did they improve their speaking skills but also their worldviews. Although English has been studied as a compulsory subject at the primary school in Uzbekistan did not have the desired effect. An education system to make students wear around the utilize of English. The childrens talk about themselves to maintain dialogue, they encourage. Dialogue and discussion by questions that help students reduce their ashamedness and reluctance to speak in English. It creates a homogeneous atmosphere in friendly and quarterly relationships. Who said one of the exact obstacles to be overcome by learners talking is worrying about risks. Mixing things that are incorrect , stupid or incomprehensible. Our mission as a teacher is to provide warmth. A climate that encourages students to speak. They can stop even break their attempts.

The approach to make speaking activities presented here demonstrates how the way towards more autonomy in language use can be prepared and motivated and

how children can be systematically guided from stages of reproductive language utilize towards creative and productive speaking. The result of research illustrates that tasks and improvisation activities are not very difficult to master for young learners ,as it is often assumed ,however have great potential to promote their communicative competence from the beginning on.

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